

On the Stability of Lithium Urate Sols.

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It was observed by Schade and Boden (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1913 83, 347) that if uric acid be suspended in boiling water, and then lithium hydroxide added to it, the acid gradually passes into the solution. On addition of sodium chloride to the colloidal lithium urate so formed, the unstable jellies of the substance are obtained. In this communication, an investigation of the substance has been made from the view point of its stability as given by coagulation and conductivity results.

The sols of lithium urate were prepared by suspending 2 g. of uric acid in 100 c.c. of conductivity water, to which a drop of phenolphthalein was added. The solution was warmed to 80-90° when lithium carbonate in very small quantities was added, till a faint pink colour just appeared. Lithium carbonate was given preference over the hydroxide on account of its insolubility. Thus a clear solution of lithium urate was obtained. It was allowed to cool slowly to the room temperature, and then filtered. The sol thus obtained is very unstable and precipitates out in the course of 20 hours. In the following table, the results on the coagulation of the sol by different electrolytes have been given.

TABLE I.

Amount of the sol taken = 2 c. c. Time of observation = 30 mins.

Total volume = 4 c. c.

Electrolyte.	Amt. required to coagulate.	Coagulating conc. in normality.
N-KCl	0.3 c. c.	0.075
N-K ₂ SO ₄	0.4	0.1
N/500-BaCl ₂	0.4	0.0002
N/110.8-Al (NO ₃) ₃	0.9	0.002025
N/66.5-H ₂ SO ₄	1.4	0.00526
N/50.Oxalic acid	0.8	0.004

Lithium urate forms a negatively charged sol. The coagulation power of the electrolytes is in the following decreasing order: $\text{BaCl}_2 > \text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 > \text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{KCl} > \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$.

The apparent anomaly of barium chloride from the well known Schulze-Hardy law is due to the chemical action between the barium salt and lithium urate.

The effect of dilution on the stability of the sol is given in the following table.

TABLE II.

Total volume = 4 c. c. Time of observation = 30 mins.

Electrolyte.	Amt. of electrolyte in c. c. to coagulate		
	1 c. c. sol.	2 c. c. sol.	2.5 c. c. sol.
N-KCl	1.0	0.3	0.15
N-K ₂ SO ₄	0.8	0.4	0.25
N/500-BaCl ₂	0.8	0.4	0.25
N/110.8 Al(NO ₃) ₃	0.6	0.9	1.1
N/66.5-H ₂ SO ₄	1.0	1.4	1.5
N/50-Oxalic acid	0.6	0.8	0.9

The results recorded in this table show that lithium urate becomes stable on dilution when coagulated by electrolytes like potassium chloride or sulphate and barium chloride. However, when the coagulation is effected by aluminium nitrate or oxalic and sulphuric acids, the concentrated sol takes up more electrolyte than the diluted sol. Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **31**, 187) have shown that the sols of antimony sulphide, prussian blue, gum dammar, and gamboge do not follow the general dilution rule and hence behave abnormally when coagulated by univalent and sometimes bivalent ions. Lithium urate also appears to belong to this abnormal class. The author has observed that while a sol obtained by suspending 2 g. of uric acid in 100 c. c. is only stable for 20 hours, the sols obtained by suspending 0.5 g. or less of uric acid in the same volume can be preserved for a number of days. It appears that on dilution, the sol preferentially adsorbs the similarly charged ions to a large extent, and it has also a marked tendency of adsorbing chloride or sulphate ions from the salts when the coagulation is affected by them. On dilution, the sol undergoes marked hydrolysis, and the uric acid thus formed is further stabilised by the adsorption of hydroxyl ions from lithium hydroxide, a product of hydrolysis.

When the sol is coagulated by potassium chloride in presence of phenolphthalein, the pink colour is intensified, showing the liberation of hydroxyl ions. The same behaviour is observed when the sol is precipitated under the ageing influence alone (*cf.* Young and Musgrave, *Biochem. J.*, 1932, **26**, 941). It has been observed that a sol having a p_H 7.6 became so much alkaline as to give a p_H 8.6 after 3 days. In the following table, the influence of ageing on the hydrogen ion concentrations of three sols prepared by the use of different amounts of lithium carbonate has been recorded.

TABLE III.

1 G. of uric acid suspended in 50 c. c. of water.

Li_2CO_3 used.	Initial p_H .	p_H after 3 days.
0.2 g.	7.5	7.9
0.22	7.6	8.6
0.25	7.9	8.8

It has also been observed that all the three sols while freshly prepared give immediately transparent jellies when mixed with potassium chloride. 3 C. c. of the sols require in the case of the first sol 0.5 c. c. of *N*-KCl; while the second and third sols give jellies with 0.2 to 0.3 c. c. of *N*-KCl. After keeping the sols for 5 hours, the jelly-forming tendency appears to disappear and the coagulum is crystalline.

An investigation has also been made on the variations in conductivities of the sol on ageing.

1 G. of uric acid was suspended in 50 c.c. of conductivity water, and in one case, 0.2 g. (I) and in the second case, 0.22 g. (II) of lithium carbonate was mixed. The mixture was warmed till a clear solution was obtained. It was then cooled and filtered and the conductivities were determined at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$. Sol I (p_H , 7.5) and sol II (p_H , 7.6) contain 0.1965 g. and 0.2139 g. of lithium urate per 10 c.c. of the sol (Table IV).

The changes in conductivity were slow when a larger amount of lithium carbonate was used. With 0.25 g. of Li_2CO_3 to 1 g. of uric acid in 50 c.c. of water, the conductivity became constant after 50 hours. The sol had an initial concentration of 0.2092 g. lithium urate per 10 c.c. and p_H 7.9. The results are given in Table V.

TABLE IV.

Time.	Conductivity in mhos.	
	Sol I.	Sol II.
1 hr.	5.516×10^{-3}	6.219×10^{-3}
3	5.439	6.16
5	5.368	6.115
6	—	6.084

TABLE V.

Time in hour	...	...	1	5	24	29	48	53
Conductivity in mhos $\times 10^3$			6.669	6.669	6.537	6.480	5.448	5.148

In the beginning, the change in conductivity was more gradual while after about 40 hours, there is a sudden drop of conductivity to almost a constant value (Table V).

The conductivity results recorded in these tables show that the ageing of the sol is always accompanied by a decrease in the electric conductivity; the greater the alkali concentration, the slower is the change. It has always been shown that the p_H of the system increases on ageing, *i.e.*, during the decomposition of the sol, some of the hydroxyl ions are set free, and in such cases an increase in the conductivity should have been expected as has been shown by Dhar and his collaborators (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 120; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 168, 209), in the case of the ageing of sols of ferric oxide, copper ferrocyanide, thorium oxide, silicic acid or arsenious sulphide. The abnormal conductivity results of lithium urate sols support the views expressed by Schade and Boden (*loc. cit.*), or Rona and Meyer (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 143, 161) who are of the opinion that about 60% of lithium urate exists as a colloid in the system and the rest as true solution, or the colloid appears to be supersaturated uric acid in which the uric acid forms an adsorption compound with the alkali. Keeser and Zocher (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1923, 17, 189), are of the view that these jelly forming urates belong to the class of electrolyte colloids. In any case, the freshly prepared lithium urate owes its high conductivity to the dissolved salt in the supersaturated state. As the ageing proceeds, the supersaturated lithium urate is removed from the system with the result that the conductivity decreases.

The jellies of lithium urate also appear to belong to the type of von Weimarn which are precipitated out from supersaturated solutions. The jelly is instantly formed and the period of gelation cannot be extended to any definite length of time. The 2% sol possesses the viscosity almost equal to that of water (0.00810 at 30°) and it does not become more viscous to any marked extent during the course of ageing or on addition of electrolytes. Thus the sol behaves as lyophobic one, and its jellies markedly differ from those obtained from lyophilic sols.

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Received December 29, 1932.

